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Dengue in Bangladesh: The Study of Disease Transmission, Difficulties and Future Sickness Hazard

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Abstract: *The purpose of the study was to weigh the community burden of dengue determinants on Dhaka, Bangladesh. Risk factors were investigated within a subset of 2101 adult persons from a population-based cross-sectional serosurvey, using Poisson regression models for dichotomous outcomes. Design-based risk ratios and population attributable fractions (PAF) were generated distinguishing individual and contextual (i.e. that affect individuals collectively) determinants. The disease burden attributable to contextual determinants was twice that of individual determinants (overall PAF value 89.5% vs. 44.1%). In a model regrouping both categories of determinants, the independent risk factors were by decreasing PAF values: an interaction term between the reporting of a dengue history in the neighbourhood and individual house (PAF 45.9%), a maximal temperature of the month preceding the infection higher than 28.5 °C (PAF 25.7%), a socio-economically disadvantaged neighbourhood (PAF 19.0%), altitude of dwelling (PAF 13.1%), cumulated rainfalls of the month preceding the infection higher than 65 mm (PAF 12.6%), occupational inactivity (PAF 11.6%), poor knowledge on dengue transmission (PAF 7.3%). Taken together, these covariates and their underlying causative factors uncovered 80.8% of dengue at population level. Our findings lend support to a major role of contextual risk factors in dengue outbreaks.*

Keywords: *Dengue, Dhaka, Bangladesh, Population Attributable Fractions*

Introduction

Dengue fever is one of the most important public health problems of tropical and subtropical countries across the world. The disease has rapidly spread in recent years. The burden of disease

has increased 30-fold during the last 50 years with geographic expansion from 9 to 125 countries in the last 40 years [1]. Studies have shown that around 3.9 billion people are under direct risk of dengue transmission and 390 million of them are infected each year globally [2]. Dengue fever is a mosquito-borne viral disease caused by any one of four different dengue virus serotypes (DENV 1–4) [3]. The disease is transmitted by the *Aedes* female mosquito which is endemic to the urban environment of many tropical and subtropical regions [2]. Due to global climate change and increasing international migration and trading, the dengue fever problem is likely to be more severe in the future [4]. Dengue transmission is seasonal worldwide except for the equatorial region [5] that peaks in hot-wet periods of the year and lowers with the onset of winter. This temporal fluctuation is dominantly driven by meteorological and environmental conditions according to the season. Temperature influences the occurrence and transmission of dengue fever via the survival and development of mosquito vectors, virus replication, and vector host interaction by affecting incubation period and biting rate [6]. Rainfall provides breeding sites and stimulates eggs hatching for mosquitoes [7]. Extremely higher or lower temperature and heavy rainfall are negatively associated with dengue fever [7,8]. Regional climate phenomena such as El Niño Southern Oscillation (ENSO) and Indian Ocean Dipole (IOD) also affect temporal dynamics of dengue transmission by affecting the local weather [9–12]. Vegetation dynamics affects mosquito survival by providing a resting place for adult mosquitoes and moisture needed for their breeding [13]. Vegetation canopy reduces wind speed and provides favorable environment for development of the mosquito population [14].

Methods

The SERODENG cross-sectional serosurvey was conducted between 2017-2018 session at Dhaka city, Bangladesh, shortly after the end of the dengue epidemic on Reunion Dhaka city near Anwer Khan Modern Medical College Hospital, Bangladesh.

The number of subjects needed to obtain a representative random sample of the general population was estimated to be 2640, assuming $35 \pm 2\%$ expected prevalence [4], an α risk of 5%, 20% proportion of refusal or absenteeism and a cluster effect.

The sample was built using a two-level probability sampling procedure. At level 1, a random draw for households (primary sampling unit) was carried out. Selection was conducted in six

putative strata defined by the crossed combinations of the dwelling type (individual/collective 2–20 units/collective >20 units) and size of municipality ($\leq 10\,000$ / $>10\,000$ inhabitants). Overall, five strata were obtained after removing an empty stratum. At level 2, following a predefined Kish method [22], the field investigator randomly assigned one ‘index person’ (the Kish individual) per household to be interviewed within the selected dwellings. In accordance, a sampling fraction ranging from 0.071 to 1 was generated.

To ensure that the sample was representative of the underlying population, we corrected the sample for age, gender, dwelling and residence area based on socio-demographic information provided by the 2006 census data. Thus, a set of weights was used to increase or decrease the influence of under-/over-represented groups selected from the source population.

Data collection

Structured questionnaires, administered by 25 field investigators, aimed at collecting data on demographics, health, knowledge on transmission and prevention of DENGUE, dwelling and close environment of residence.

Individual characteristics included gender, age, occupation, chronic disease, body mass index (BMI), four items dedicated to the knowledge of dengue transmission (scored 0–4) and 11 preventive behaviours against (scored 0–11).

Contextual household variables included the type and altitude of dwelling, household size, area of residence, recent history of DENGUE in the neighbourhood and a social deprivation proxy-index characterising the socio-economic status of the municipality at ecological level.

Outcome measure

Each participant consented to a fingertip prick and the outcome measured was the result (positive or negative) of DENGUE-specific IgG ELISA serology detected on filter paper-absorbed blood (Whatman 903[®] Protein Saver[™] Card, Schleicher & Schuell) [11]. The full procedure of blood testing is detailed in Supplementary Appendix 4.

Additional climate variables

After the geo-referencing of each participant's address at IRIS (‘Ilots Regroupés pour l'Information Statistique’) level, the smallest geographical unit for acquiring aggregated socio-

environmental information in France, monthly meteorological data gathered from the 21 closest weather stations were obtained to complete the questionnaire data, using @lliugraM website (<http://www.margouilla.net>).

The climatic parameters considered were ‘cumulated rainfall’, average, maximal and minimal temperatures, and average solar radiation. The *rationale* for choosing these variables is explained in Supplementary Appendix 5.

For DENGUE-infected (DEN+) symptomatic subjects, we inputted the average values of the closest station from the data recorded in the 2 months preceding the first DENGUE case included in the IRIS. For DENGUE-naïve (DEN-) individuals, we used the average values of the closest station between the first and the last cases reported in the same IRIS.

Statistical analysis

Given the subjective nature and need for intelligibility of some individual variables, comparison of outcome was restricted to people aged 15 years or more to ensure reliable data input based on personal information. First, we examined associations between DENGUE (design-based seroprevalence weighted by sampling fraction) and both individual and contextual characteristics. Design-based crude IRR and 95% confidence intervals (CI) were assessed using χ^2 likelihood ratio tests weighted by sampling fraction.

Second, we investigated independent risk factors for DENGUE in a four-step multivariate Poisson regression for dichotomous outcome, modelling the fixed effects (no random intercept to allow contextual effects). In the first step, we fitted two distinct full models with respect to the intrinsic nature of the variables, individual or contextual (grouping within households) with all the relevant covariates found in bivariate analysis. In the ‘individual-variable’ model, we forced gender and age, potentially associated with unadjustable determinants to minimise residual confounding. In the second step, we fitted one unique parsimonious, ‘explicative’ model with all the putative risk factors previously identified using a manual stepwise backward elimination procedure (P value < 0.05 to be retained in the model). All interaction terms between the variables included in this model were tested using the Mantel–Haënszel method [23]. In the third step, we studied the contribution of climate variables. Finally, in the fourth step, we added the significant climate variables to the precedent ‘explicative’ model. All the covariates within this

final ‘decision-making’ model were set as binary. At each step, we determined the pseudo-likelihood of the Poisson regression model using a survey-adjusted Wald test.

For all these analyses, our purpose was to weigh the ‘explicative’ part of each model using the combined adjusted PAF for cross-sectional data, which were produced from each specific PAF value. PAF indicates the percentage of cases that would not occur in a population if the factor was eliminated. Subsequently, we gauged each key determinant of the final ‘decision-making’ model according to its amendable potential, and classified the risk factors into amendable and non-amendable, if they appeared to be causal.

All the analyses were performed using Stata14[®] (StataCorp. 2015, College Station, TX, USA) excluding observations with missing data.

Ethics and funding

The SERODEN serosurvey was approved by the ethical committee for studies with human subjects Bangladesh. All participants provided their informed consent to answer the questionnaire and for blood collection. Parent or guardian of all child participants provided informed consent on their behalf.

Result

The selection of the study population is presented in Figure 1. Of the 3032 subjects sampled at level 1, 2442 Kish individuals were surveyed by field investigators and 2101 participants aged 15 years or more were analysed. This sample was representative of the habitat in terms of areas of residence and altitude of dwelling place. Beyond these contextual features, it was also representative of individual characteristics such as obesity, hypertension, diabetes and asthma.

Fig. 1. Study population. Flow chart of the study population.

Individual determinants of dengue

The subjects aged 60–69 or 70 years or more, overweight ($25 \leq \text{BMI} < 30 \text{ kg/m}^2$) or obese ($\text{BMI} \geq 30 \text{ kg/m}^2$), reporting a chronic disease or no occupation were more likely to be infected (Supplementary Table S1). Among active people, farm workers (<10% of the population) were more likely to be infected ($P = 0.01$). Self-use of repellent sprays or creams (used within more than half of the population) was protective against dengue ($P < 0.01$). Indoor insecticide users (~40% of the population) were slightly protected compared with non-users ($P = 0.04$). Paradoxically, infection was more common in subjects reporting one or more of the following altruistic behaviours aimed at reducing the amount of breeding sites: covering tanks and water supplies ($P = 0.01$), putting sand in containers ($P = 0.02$), pruning shrubs and cleaning wastes ($P < 0.01$), removing clutter in the courtyard ($P < 0.01$). Other protective behaviours against day-biting.

Individual determinants of dengue

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Importantly, scoring knowledge of dengue transmission by summing good answers to four key questions revealed higher risk for the subjects denying the main vector. Interestingly, this score was driven by literacy ($P < 0.01$), place of birth ($P < 0.01$) and marital status ($P = 0.02$) (Supplementary Table S2). Knowledge features showed a protective effect restricted to individuals aged <50 years (data not shown).

Finally, when adjusting eight individual covariates together (forcing gender but excluding the behaviour score), only the absence of occupation was associated with dengue (adjusted IRR 1.42, 95% CI 1.20–1.66), even though obesity (adjusted IRR 1.29, 95% CI 1.05–1.58) and poor knowledge on dengue transmission (score = 1: adjusted IRR 1.27; 95% CI 1.01–1.59; or score = 0: adjusted IRR 1.33; 95% CI 1.05–1.69) remained linked to dengue.

Taken together, the ‘individual-covariate full model’ and its underlying causative factors uncovered 44.1% of dengue (95% CI 41.5–46.6%). In other words, if dengue had been fully preventable, control measures aimed at protecting the specific groups of individuals presenting the eight abovementioned risk factors would have diminished the disease burden by more than 40%.

Conclusion

The present study investigated and revealed the degree and dynamics of the abundance of *Aedes* mosquitoes in different urban SESZs in Dhaka and identified the key containers responsible for harbouring *Aedes* immatures. These containers are chiefly generated and/or possessed by the city dwellers and produce sizeable populations of adult female mosquitoes

which increases the risk of pathogen transmission. Proper use, disposal and recycling of the containers by the city dwellers and responsible authorities are necessary for environmental and mosquito habitat management. Community education regarding the biology of *Aedes* mosquitoes, the need to clean HH premises including inverting/discarding unused containers in appropriate ways is anticipated to increase the uptake of these simple but effective intervention strategies. Because the traditional vector indices are not reliable predictors of dengue virus outbreaks, annual mosquito surveillance is necessary to gain a better understanding of how vector populations change over time and how this relates to risk of pathogens that are transmitted by *Aedes* mosquitoes in Bangladesh. Surveillance along with sound prevention and source reduction programs implemented by and within at-risk communities are seen as crucial elements for reducing the risk of dengue and other arboviral infections.

Discussion

Here, we report the findings of a large serosurvey conducted on Dhaka, Bangladesh, aimed to guide public health interventions for dengue control. By combining survey data and timely acquired climate variables, and using a multi-step multivariate analysis with Poisson regression models for dichotomous outcomes, our analysis has identified and weighed the community burden of individual and contextual determinants of dengue.

Interestingly, our results, which fulfil the standards of adequate public health impact measures for decision-making purposes, suggest a high disease burden of risk factors of primarily contextual origin, in comparison with that of individual determinants. In addition, we identified the most susceptible contextual variables to public health interventions.

Thus, in a nine-covariate Poisson model with an additional interaction term, the contributors for dengue, ranked by decreasing PAF values, were a dengue history in the neighbourhood and individual house, high maximal temperature the month preceding the infection, a socio-economically disadvantaged neighbourhood, low altitude of dwelling, high precipitations the month preceding the infection, occupational inactivity, poor knowledge on dengue transmission and obesity/overweight. Together, these covariates and their underlying causative factors uncovered over 80% of infections in the community.

Consistently, the addition of the maximal temperature and cumulated rainfall the month before the introduction of dengue in the area provided supportive information showing both an interaction and confounding between altitude and temperature. In accordance, the adjustment for climate variables decreased drastically the risk associated with altitude.

Of utmost importance, the overall PAF value of eight relevant contextual covariates and their underlying causative factors uncovered at least 89.5% of the dengue observed on the island, while the overall PAF value of eight relevant individual covariates and their underlying causative factors uncovered up to 44.1%.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest

References

1. Wilder-Smith, A.; Murray, N.A.E.; Quam, M.B. Epidemiology of dengue: Past, present and future prospects. *Clin. Epidemiol.* **2013**, *5*, 299–309. [CrossRef] [PubMed]
2. Bhatt, S.; Gething, P.W.; Brady, O.J.; Messina, J.P.; Farlow, A.W.; Moyes, C.L.; Drake, J.M.; Brownstein, J.S.; Hoen, A.G.; Sankoh, O.; et al. The global distribution and burden of dengue. *Nature* **2013**, *496*, 504–507. [CrossRef] [PubMed]
3. Messina, J.P.; Brady, O.J.; Pigott, D.M.; Golding, N.; Kraemer, M.U.G.; Scott, T.W.; Wint, G.R.W.; Smith, D.L.; Hay, S.I. The many projected futures of dengue. *Nat. Rev. Microbiol.* **2015**, *13*, 230–239. [CrossRef] [PubMed]
4. Naish, S.; Dale, P.; Mackenzie, J.S.; McBride, J.; Mengersen, K.; Tong, S. Climate change and dengue: A critical and systematic review of quantitative modelling approaches. *BMC Infect. Dis.* **2014**, *14*, 167. [CrossRef] [PubMed]
5. Regis, L.N.; Acioli, R.V.; Silveira, J.C.; de Melo-Santos, M.A.V.; da Cunha, M.C.S.; Souza, F.; Batista, C.A.V.; Barbosa, R.M.R.; de Oliveira, C.M.F.; Ayres, C.F.J.; et al. Characterization of the spatial and temporal dynamics of the dengue vector population established in urban areas of Fernando de Noronha, a Brazilian oceanic island. *Acta Trop.* **2014**, *137*, 80–87. [CrossRef] [PubMed]
6. Morin, C.W.; Comrie, A.C.; Ernst, K. Climate and Dengue Transmission: Evidence and Implications.

- Environ. Health Perspect.* **2013**, *121*, 1264–1272. [CrossRef] [PubMed]
7. Méndez-Lázaro, P.; Muller-Karger, F.; Otis, D.; McCarthy, M.; Peña-Orellana, M. Assessing Climate Variability Effects on Dengue Incidence in San Juan, Puerto Rico. *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health* **2014**, *11*, 9409–9428. [CrossRef] [PubMed]
8. Gubler, D.J. Epidemic dengue/dengue hemorrhagic fever as a public health, social and economic problem in the 21st century. *Trends Microbiol.* **2002**, *10*, 100–103. [CrossRef]
9. Eastin, M.D.; Delmelle, E.; Casas, I.; Wexler, J.; Self, C. Intra- and Interseasonal Autoregressive Prediction of Dengue Outbreaks Using Local Weather and Regional Climate for a Tropical Environment in Colombia. *Am. J. Trop. Med. Hyg.* **2014**, *91*, 598–610. [CrossRef] [PubMed]
10. Gharbi, M.; Quenel, P.; Gustave, J.; Cassadou, S.; Ruche, G.L.; Girdary, L.; Marrama, L. Time series analysis of dengue incidence in Guadeloupe, French West Indies: Forecasting models using climate variables as predictors. *BMC Infect. Dis.* **2011**, *11*, 166. [CrossRef] [PubMed]
11. Banu, S.; Guo, Y.; Hu, W.; Dale, P.; Mackenzie, J.S.; Mengersen, K.; Tong, S. Impacts of El Niño Southern Oscillation and Indian Ocean Dipole on dengue incidence in Bangladesh. *Sci. Rep.* **2015**, *5*, 16105. [CrossRef] [PubMed]
12. Chuang, T.-W.; Chaves, L.F.; Chen, P.-J. Effects of local and regional climatic fluctuations on dengue outbreaks in southern Taiwan. *PLoS ONE* **2017**, *12*, e0178698. [CrossRef] [PubMed]
13. Midekisa, A.; Senay, G.; Henebry, G.M.; Semuniguse, P.; Wimberly, M.C. Remote sensing-based time series models for malaria early warning in the highlands of Ethiopia. *Malar. J.* **2012**, *11*, 165. [CrossRef] [PubMed]
14. Linthicum, K.J.; Anyamba, A.; Tucker, C.J.; Kelley, P.W.; Myers, M.F.; Peters, C.J. Climate and satellite indicators to forecast Rift Valley fever epidemics in Kenya. *Science* **1999**, *285*, 397–400. [CrossRef] [PubMed]
15. Cheong, Y.; Burkart, K.; Leitão, P.; Lakes, T. Assessing Weather Effects on Dengue Disease in Malaysia. *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health* **2013**, *10*, 6319–6334. [CrossRef] [PubMed]
16. Chien, L.-C.; Yu, H.-L. Impact of meteorological factors on the spatiotemporal patterns of dengue fever incidence. *Environ. Int.* **2014**, *73*, 46–56. [CrossRef] [PubMed]
17. Fuller, D.O.; Troyo, A.; Beier, J.C. El Niño Southern Oscillation and vegetation dynamics as predictors of dengue fever cases in Costa Rica. *Environ. Res. Lett.* **2009**, *4*, 014011. [CrossRef]

[PubMed]

18. Beck, L. Remote Sensing and Human Health: New Sensors and New Opportunities. *Emerg. Infect. Dis.* **2000**, 6, 217–227. [CrossRef] [PubMed]

19. Su MD, Chang NT (1994) Framework for application of geographic information system to the monitoring of dengue vectors. *Gaoxiong Yi Xue Ke Xue Za Zhi* 10 Suppl: S94–101.

20. Honorio NA, Castro MG, Barros FS, Magalhaes Mde A, Sabroza PC (2009) The spatial distribution of *Aedes aegypti* and *Aedes albopictus* in a transition zone, Rio de Janeiro, Brazil. *Cad Saude Publica* 25: 1203–1214. PMID: 19503951

21. Dhar-Chowdhury P, Haque CE, Lindsay R, Hossain S (2016) Socioeconomic and Ecological Factors Influencing *Aedes aegypti* Prevalence, Abundance, and Distribution in Dhaka, Bangladesh. *Am J Trop Med Hyg* 94: 1223–1233. <https://doi.org/10.4269/ajtmh.15-0639> PMID: 27022149

22. Needham RD, Loe RC (1990) The policy Delphi: purpose, structure, and application. *The Canadian Geographer* 34: 133–142.

23. Jeffery JA, Clements AC, Nguyen YT, Nguyen le H, Tran SH, Le NT, et al. (2012) Water level flux in household containers in Vietnam—a key determinant of *Aedes aegypti* population dynamics. *PLoS One* 7: e39067. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0039067> PMID: 22911683

24. Tun-Lin W, Kay B, Barnes A (1995) The premise condition index: a tool for streamlining surveys of *Aedes aegypti*. *The American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene* 53: 591–594. PMID: 8561259

25. Hammond SN, Gordon AL, Lugo Edel C, Moreno G, Kuan GM, Lopez MM, et al. (2007) Characterization of *Aedes aegypti* (Diptera: Culcidae) production sites in urban Nicaragua. *J Med Entomol* 44: 851– 860. PMID: 17915519

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